

Statistical Analysis of Dengue Transmission Dynamics in Colombo Municipal Council (CMC) Area, Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Dengue fever is a major public health concern in tropical regions, with its incidence strongly influenced by environmental factors. In this study, we investigated the role of climate variables such as rainfall, temperature, and humidity in shaping dengue dynamics using statistical time series methods. Prior to conducting all statistical analyses, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test was used to check the stationarity of the exogenous variables. Granger causality analysis revealed that all three climate variables significantly predict dengue incidence, highlighting their importance in forecasting outbreaks. An ARIMAX model incorporating these exogenous climate variables, along with lagged dengue cases, was developed to reconstruct the temporal dynamics of dengue incidence. Model validation across the entire study period yielded a mean absolute error (MAE) of 15.93 cases and a root mean squared error (RMSE) of 22.73 cases, demonstrating that the model captures general trends effectively. These results indicate that the proposed ARIMAX framework can serve as a useful tool for analyzing dengue transmission dynamics. In future work, we plan to extend this framework by developing hybrid models that combine statistical approaches with mechanistic epidemiological models.

Keywords: Dengue transmission, GC test, ADF test, ARIMAX model

1. Introduction

Dengue is a viral infection caused by the dengue virus (DENV), which is transmitted to humans through the bite of infected mosquitoes. Approximately half of the world's population is now at risk of contracting dengue, with an estimated 100-400 million infections occurring annually. Dengue is found in tropical and subtropical climates worldwide, mostly in urban and semi-urban areas. While many DENV infections are asymptomatic or produce only mild illness, DENV can occasionally cause more severe cases, and even death. Because of that, prevention and control of dengue rely on vector control. There is no specific treatment for dengue/severe dengue, and early detection and access to proper medical care greatly lower fatality rates of severe dengue [1]. Dengue is a public health problem in Sri Lanka, with over 50 000 cases reported each year in the recent past. The country has been successful in bringing down the Case Fatality Rate (CFR) over the last two decades, which was around from 5% in 1996 to 1% in 2009, and has declined gradually over time to 0.07% in 2023 [2]. It shows the resilience and high capacity of the curative sector in managing dengue patients. However, the country experiences rising cases during the rainy seasons in June-July and October-December every year. During the years, almost all districts of the country have reported the highest dengue cases, with Western Province, particularly the Colombo Municipal Council (CMC) area [3]. High population density, rapid urbanization, and favorable climatic conditions create an environment that supports intense *Aedes* mosquito breeding and sustained virus transmission. Despite decades of prevention strategies, including vector control and minimizing human–vector interactions, dengue continues to pose a significant public health challenge in Sri Lanka and beyond. Epidemiological studies indicate that outbreaks are strongly influenced by climatic conditions such as rainfall,

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temperature, and humidity [3,4,5]. Conventionally, dengue transmission has been described through classical compartmental models, most notably the SIR (Susceptible–Infectious–Recovered) framework [6]. But these compartment models require assumptions about biological parameters and vector host interactions. Statistical methods, like ARIMAX models, provide a practical way to understand dengue dynamics by analyzing how past cases and environmental factors influence the disease over time [4]. This study aims to analyze the dengue transmission dynamics by using statistical methods in the Colombo Municipal Council (CMC) area in Sri Lanka.

2. Study Area and Data Collection

Study Area

The analysis of dengue transmission was done focusing on the Colombo Municipal Council, the main urban and economic center of Sri Lanka. The Colombo Municipal Council (CMC) is located on the west coast of the island. The CMC area stands out for its high population density and intense urban activity, with a population of 561,314 living within a 37 km² area according to the 2012 Census [7]. The climate of Colombo is tropical. The average annual temperature is between 27°C and 29°C, and the daily maximum temperature is around 31°C [8]. The area receives about 2,523.7 mm of rainfall per year. Colombo is affected by two main monsoon seasons. The South-West monsoon occurs from May to September [9], and the North-East monsoon occurs from December to February [10]. In addition, public transport systems connect Colombo with other key cities in Sri Lanka. Hence, viral diseases can be easily transmitted from Colombo to other cities due to high human mobility rates. Figure 1 shows the Colombo Municipal Council (CMC) area map. Due to these favorable conditions, dengue transmission is facilitated in this region.

Figure 1: Map of the CMC area [11]

Data Analysis

Weekly dengue cases of the CMC area were obtained from Epidemology department of Sri Lanka, and the time period covered from 2016 to 2024. Metrological variables, including temperature, rainfall, and humidity collected from the NASA POWER Access Viewer. A moving average filter was applied to smooth the data, reducing random noise

while preserving key trends. Figure 2 shows the weekly number of dengue cases, rainfall, average temperature, and humidity data for the Colombo CMC area from 2016 to 2024. Before applying the statistical method, it is important to measure the correlation between meteorological factors and dengue cases. To calculate the time delay, the Pearson correlation coefficient and the Spearman correlation coefficient can be used. The Pearson correlation coefficient is the standard coefficient that can be used to measure the strength of the linear relationship between two variables [12]. The Spearman correlation coefficient can be used to compute the strength of the relationship between two variables. However, the Spearman correlation coefficient is equal to the Pearson correlation coefficient between the rank values of those two variables. Therefore, we have used the Spearman cross-correlation formula to measure the correlation between the meteorological factors and dengue incidences [13]. The correlation measure with time lags from 0 to 25 weeks has been plotted. Figures 3,4, and 5 show the time lag between dengue incidences and meteorological factors such as temperature, rainfall, and humidity. It can be observed that the time lags are 14 weeks for temperature, 5 weeks for rainfall, and 11 weeks for humidity, and we use dengue incidences with a 4-week time delay.

Figure 2: (a) Weekly dengue cases, (b) rainfall, (c) average temperature, and (d) humidity data for the Colombo CMC area from 2016 to 2024

Figure 3: (a) Correlation between dengue cases and temperature, (b) Correlation between dengue cases and rainfall, (c) Correlation between dengue cases and humidity

3. Materials and Mathematical Models

Granger Causality Analysis

Before fitting the ARIMAX model, we need to investigate whether climatic variables significantly contribute to the prediction of dengue incidence. Then we applied the Granger Causality (GC) test. The GC test is a statistical test that determines if the past values of one time series (rainfall, temperature, humidity) provide statistically significant information to forecast another series (weekly dengue cases) [14]. Before conducting this test, the stationarity of each series was verified using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The test used the following hypotheses. (i) Null hypothesis (H0): The series is not stationary (contains a unit root). (ii) Alternative hypothesis (H1): The series is stationary (doesn't contain a unit root). If the null hypothesis is rejected, then the time series is stationary. This happens when the test statistics are lower than the critical value, and the p-value is below 0.05. Once stationarity was confirmed, the GC test was applied. The general form of the GC test is as follows:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i Y_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad (1)$$

Here, α_0 is a constant, α_i and β_i are the coefficient parameters of X and Y respectively. μ_t is the white noise and p, q are the maximum lags considered for the variables.

ARIMAX model

The model ARIMAX extends the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), incorporating exogenous variables, which are defined to be external variables or predictors that are not part of the time series. While they are not as frequent in certain fields, they can make a huge difference in the time series. This integration enables the model to leverage more information that could significantly enhance the prediction. The ARIMAX model used in our study is represented by Equation (2).

$$Y_t = \delta + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_{k,t-lagk} + \sum_{p=1}^P \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \sum_{q=1}^Q \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \quad (2)$$

Y_t is the number of dengue cases at week t , $X_{k,t-lagk}$ is the exogenous variables with lags, β_k is the coefficients of exogenous variables, ϕ_p is the coefficient corresponding to the lag of the dependent variable Y , θ_q coefficient for the q -th lag of the residual term ϵ , δ is the intercept, the total number of exogenous variables is denoted by K , the maximum lag of the dependent variable is P , and the maximum lag of the residuals is Q . The ARIMAX model was fitted using maximum likelihood estimation in Python's *statsmodels* package.

4. Results and Discussion

To investigate the causal relationship between dengue cases with metrological data, we performed the GC test. Before doing this, first checked the stationarity of the exogenous variables using the ADF test. The ADF test proved that the time series of the weekly dengue cases, rainfall, temperature, and humidity were stationary, which is shown in Table 1. The stationary time series ensures the reliability and applicability of these time series to conduct the prediction of dengue transmission.

	Weekly Dengue cases	Rainfall	Temperature	Humidity
Test Statistic	-2.912915	-7.719428	-7.193226	-5.957998

p- value	0.043866644456629	0.00000000012037	0.000000000247245	0.000000207110039
Conclusion	Stationary	Stationary	Stationary	Stationary

Table 1: ADF test results for dengue cases, rainfall, temperature, and humidity.

After performing the ADF test, the GC test was employed. A relationship such as Rainfall → Dengue Cases indicates that the rainfall time series Granger-causes the dengue incidence time series. Similarly, tests for Temperature → Dengue Cases and Humidity → Dengue Cases were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that past values of these climate variables help predict dengue cases. In contrast, the reverse relationships, where dengue incidence was tested as a predictor of rainfall, temperature, or humidity, were generally not significant ($p > 0.05$). Table 3 shows the results taken from the GC test. The results indicate that the rainfall, temperature, and humidity have a significant effect on dengue cases. Reverse causality tests, in which dengue cases were tested as a predictor of the climate variables, showed some statistical significance for rainfall and temperature; however, these are likely reflect seasonal patterns and correlations rather than true causal effects. This demonstrates a one-way Granger causality from the climate variables to dengue incidence. In other words, historical rainfall, temperature, and humidity provide valuable information for predicting dengue outbreaks, which can be used in statistical models of dengue transmission dynamics and to improve early-warning and forecasting systems for dengue incidence.

Relationship	Rainfall → Dengue Cases p-value: 1.17×10^{-11}	Dengue Cases → Rainfall p-value: 0.0021
Relationship	Temperature → Dengue Cases p-value: 0.0050	Dengue Cases → Temperature p-value: 0.0011
Relationship	Humidity → Dengue Cases p-value: 0.0012	Dengue Cases → Humidity p-value: 0.178

Table 2: GC test results for dengue cases, rainfall, temperature, and humidity

After performing all statistical tests for the exogenous variables ARIMAX model was used to capture the dengue transmission dynamic in the CMC area. Using rainfall, temperature, and humidity along with lagged dengue cases, the ARIMAX model successfully captured the temporal dynamics of dengue incidence. As shown in Figure 4, the fitted model closely followed observed weekly dengue cases, reflecting both seasonal trends and the effects of climate drivers.

Figure 4: Comparison with observed dengue cases with ARIMAX fitted cases in the CMC area from 2016 to 2025.

To evaluate the predictive performance of the ARIMAX model, we compared the fitted dengue cases with the observed cases for the year 2024, which is shown in Figure 5. The model captured the overall dynamics of dengue incidence, including the timing and magnitude of the major peaks. Validation metrics indicated a mean absolute error (MAE) of 11.95 cases and a root mean squared error (RMSE) of 15.89 cases, demonstrating that the ARIMAX model provides a reasonably accurate reconstruction of weekly dengue trends. These results confirm that the inclusion of rainfall, temperature, and humidity as exogenous variables allows the model to effectively quantify dengue dynamics and supports its use for forecasting purposes. However, the ARIMAX model was limited in representing the detailed transmission dynamics of dengue due to factors such as complex vector–host interactions, human mobility, and unmeasured environmental influences. To address these limitations, we propose the development of a hybrid modeling framework that integrates ARIMAX with mechanistic epidemiological models. This approach is expected to provide more accurate forecasts and better insights into the mechanisms driving dengue transmission, supporting effective early-warning and intervention strategies.

Figure 5: Predictive performance of the ARIMAX model in 2024 dengue cases.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we analyzed the dynamics of dengue incidence in relation to climate variables using a combination of Granger causality tests and an ARIMAX model. The Granger causality analysis demonstrated that rainfall, temperature, and humidity significantly predict dengue incidence, confirming the importance of these climate drivers in forecasting dengue trends. The ARIMAX model, which incorporated these exogenous variables along with lagged dengue cases, was able to reconstruct the overall temporal patterns of dengue incidence. Validation across the entire study period showed a mean absolute error (MAE) of 15.93 cases and a root mean squared error (RMSE) of 22.73 instances, indicating that the model performs reasonably well in capturing general trends. Overall, these results confirm that climate-informed statistical time-series modeling is a useful and reliable approach for predicting dengue transmission dynamics. This approach provides a strong quantitative basis for supporting surveillance and early warning activities in dengue-endemic regions.

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